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Abstract

The research explored the effective methods that lecturers and educators can employ to assess university students, in the context of artificial intelligence (AI) chatbots. The field of artificial intelligence has been rapidly growing. The rapid growth has wrought interactive tools such as ChatGPT, a text based interactive tool that generates human like responses based on user text input. ChatGPT was launched not so long ago, in November 2022 but has attracted millions of users, world over. Chatbots like ChatGPT are able to give responses to complex essay questions, programming problems and even business ideas in a way that mimics the student writing the response on their own. Lecturers and educators now have to rethink and restructure the type of assessments that they assign to students. The traditional methods of assessing university students might not produce the intended results according to set university pedagogical goals. Students' use of AI chatbots to write answers to assessments given by educators has the greatest potential to negatively impact key academic areas such as critical thinking, development of research skills, and becoming a lifelong learner. Hence the need for an exploration of approaches, strategies, techniques and methods to assess students amidst the usage of artificial intelligence tools. The research involved an extensive literature review on the subject followed by collection of qualitative data on the views of both educators and learners from universities in Ndola, Zambia. The study population comprised two universities in Ndola, from which a sample size of 25 participants was drawn, based on attaining saturation point. The research findings could benefit university faculty as they will have a guide on what type of assessments to assign students and how to evaluate student responses. In addition, other non-academic institutions that create assessments could also find the findings useful in that

they may be assessing individuals who might be versed with artificial intelligence tools. Higher education policies can be formulated based on the findings of this research.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, ChatGPT, Chatbot, assessment, generative AI

Exploring Effective Methods Of Assessing University Students Amidst AI Usage

Computer technology has been revolutionizing how industry professionals perform their tasks and duties in respective fields ranging from manufacturing, service, health and education. One branch of computer technology that has been rapidly growing and transforming how companies operate in their day to day activities is Artificial Intelligence (AI). On November 30th 2022, the company OpenAI released a version of generative AI called ChatGPT. This AI tool for the first time in the history of computer technology had the capability of producing human-like responses in a conversational format. The tool can also remember previous responses and inputs and be able to provide more meaningful responses such as admitting to incorrect responses, challenging incorrect viewpoints, and being able to reject inappropriate input (OpenAI, 2022).

The release of ChatGPT was followed with numerous reviews from individuals and corporate entities worldwide. It did not take long for people to realize that the new AI tool can be utilized to write project plans, business ideas, and cover letters for jobs and summarize stories and essays. As people interacted with ChatGPT in the first few weeks after the release, they identified a few pitfalls in the new AI tool. It was identified that ChatGPT had a tendency of creating false responses due to the unavailability of requested data (Mollick, 2022).

In addition to the pitfalls such as false responses, ChatGPT was also identified to have biases based on the data that it was trained on. These biases range from racially or ethnically inclined statements, gender inclined statements, and religious based stereotypical statements. ChatGPT based on GPT-3.5 seemed to have been enhanced on the predecessor's GPT version, which was GPT-2 (Lau & Guo, 2023; Liang, Morency, & Salakhutdinov, 2021). Microsoft

(2023) in their report on governing AI - a blueprint for the future, they present some guidelines on AI usage as AI progresses in this era. Microsoft (2023) states that the corporate entities in countries should be considering questions such as how can we harness this new technology to solve complex problems? How can new problems created by the new technology be avoided or managed? How can companies remain in control of the ever growing powerful technology? One of the guardrails among the five points for governing AI is “promoting transparency and ensuring academic and nonprofit access to AI” in which it is stated that universities need access to critical technology infrastructure such as AI to advance in scientific and technological research (Microsoft, 2023). In the report by Microsoft it can be clearly observed that AI will be in existence even in the coming decades.

Background

The year 2023 started on a very high note for a number of universities across the globe due to the fact that students caught up with the generative artificial intelligence tool - ChatGPT. Just like how working professionals caught up with the tool on speeding up their work and delivering task outputs with efficiency, students noticed that they could query the tool to write assignments for them in a very short time period. Students started querying ChatGPT to write essay type assignments, and some went to the extent of querying ChatGPT during their online exams. This caused a lot of panic in a number of universities around the world because they did not know how to manage the rapid increase in ChatGPT usage among the students. The concerns were that students would not learn imperative skills of critical thinking and problem solving and also mitigating academic dishonesty. The concerns led to a lot of universities and education districts to block school computer networks from accessing ChatGPT and other related generative artificial intelligence chatbots (Johnson, 2023; Korn & Kelly, 2023; Nolan, 2023).

While that can look like a solution, it was argued by Roose (2023) that instead of blocking it, teachers can utilize ChatGPT as a teaching aid. Roose (2023) argued that ChatGPT can unlock student creativity potentials that teachers are not aware of by blocking it. In addition to that he argued that regardless of blocking accessibility to ChatGPT on the school computer networks, students still have access to ChatGPT on their smartphones and laptops. Therefore, blocking ChatGPT on school computer networks is not the solution (Johnson, 2023; Roose, 2023).

According to pedagogical teaching principles, students have to be engaged and motivated in the learning process, and the teachers should ensure that students are assessed based on their level of understanding. Consequently, when students have interacted with the course material and they have acquainted themselves with the course textbooks and adequately covered the course objectives, then they can be assessed according to the bloom's taxonomy levels. (Heny & Pennock, 2023) However, if students can easily query a generative artificial intelligence tool when answering assessment questions, it defeats the purpose of pedagogical goals and bloom's taxonomy levels of assessing students.

Problem Statement

The current assessment methods in higher education institutions are becoming ineffective amidst the usage of generative AI tools such as ChatGPT (Todeschini et al, 2023). Computer technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) have revolutionized how people complete their tasks. ChatGPT, a generative version of AI, has the capability of producing human-like responses in a conversational format. This has led to students having their assignment/assessment responses generated by ChatGPT which they in turn submit as their own. The objectives for student assessments include assessment of knowledge, critical thinking skills, research skills and problem solving skills amongst others. Student assessments therefore aim to bridge the gap between theory and practice by assessing how

students are able to apply the concepts learnt. However, the usage of AI tools such as ChatGPT counteracts these intended objectives because ChatGPT is able to generate responses and solutions for the students without them putting in any effort. This research therefore aims to explore effective assessment methods that can be realized in order to ensure that the intended objectives are still met.

Research Objectives

1. To investigate and assess the knowledge and usage of AI among faculty and students in the context of higher education institutions.
2. To critically assess the effectiveness of current assessment methods employed by higher education institutions in Ndola amidst AI usage.
3. To explore effective assessment methods for students in higher education institutions amidst AI usage in Ndola.

Research Questions

1. How do faculty and students perceive and utilize AI within the context of higher education institutions?
2. How effective are current student assessment methods employed in higher education institutions amidst AI usage?
3. What assessment methods for students in higher education institutions would be effective amidst AI usage?

Research Significance

This research can benefit university faculty as it provides methods and approaches on what type of assessments to assign students and how to evaluate their responses. It can also serve as a guide for other non-academic institutions that create assessments. Higher education policies can also be formulated based on the findings of this research.

Literature Review and Conceptual Framework

Literature Review

Effectiveness of current assessment methods

The higher education has been transformed by generative AI. According to Heny and Pencook (2023), since its introduction in 2023, faculty and students have been impacted in the way they teach and learn respectively. Heny and Peacock (2023) further state that as the abilities of AI continue to improve, so has the usage among students and faculty reporting that 42% of students who were surveyed admitted to using AI for their course work in one way or another. The objectives of assessments include application of knowledge, developing critical thinking, problem solving and research skills, self-directed learning and enhancing communication skills. With the capabilities that AI possesses, students are able to ask the AI tools such as ChatGPT to respond to a question exactly as needed thereby hampering the objectives set for assignments. Heny and Peacock (2023) emphasizes that if AI is not used correctly, students will end up learning less than they currently do. Cardona et al, (2023) states that there has been an increasing interest in the usage of AI in the education sector suggesting that educators must seek technologically enhanced approaches to enhance their teaching methodologies. Cardona et al, (2023) further emphasizes that educators should not shun generative AI tools but rather continue to explore how AI tools can improve learning outcomes by harnessing the good out of AI tools. To effectively do so is to understand the challenges with current assessment methods and protect the learners against the dangers that may arise with the abuse of AI generative tools usage. Bridgeman et al, (2023) in their report mention that one of the challenges with current assessment methods with AI generative tools is that there is fear that this new technology that is able to produce human-like responses will encourage cheating and undermine academic integrity. The major concern is the tool's ability to produce a complete finished essay when given a topic and asked to do (Bridgeman et al,

2023). In an article in the Guardian newspaper, Dan Gillmor who is a Journalism professor tested an assignment he gives to his students on ChatGPT and he said he would have given a very good grade of the response. According to Swiecki et al (2022), it is important for educators to create well designed assessments in order to determine whether students have learnt. Swiecki et al (2022) argues that current traditional assessment methods have several issues such as inauthenticity and inability to provide nuanced views of learning thus suggesting that several applications of AI tools have come in handy to partially address these challenges. Swiecki et al (2022) however cautiously noted that traditional assessment tools were created for a reason and have been successful in evaluating and improving student learning and thus should not be rendered obsolete. Mislevy and colleagues as cited by Swiecki et al (2022) state that educational assessments are mostly set within the standard assessment paradigm and the commonly used assessments include multiple choice questions, essays and short answer questions. Swiecki et al (2022) further state that as much as these methods are commonly and currently used, they do have several potential problems. In summary, the several potential problems being discussed are that current assessment methods are discrete, uniform, isolated and antiquated (Swiecki et al, 2022).

It is a given that AI tools such as ChatGPT have triggered debates on plagiarism and cheating in academia with others suggesting that it is indeed plagiarism and others suggesting it is not. Lee (2023) discusses that AI models for detecting plagiarism are being developed and until then, the workload rests with faculty for them to deal with challenges in detecting whether the students have presented AI generated work or not. Lee (2023) further suggests that lecturers need to be trained on new assessment practices in response to the challenges that were being experienced with student's usage of AI tools like ChatGPT. Owan et al (2023) states that there is an increased concern that AI tools are able to generate responses

that cannot be detected by a plagiarism checker and there are currently no methods to differentiate between content generated by AI and content generated by humans.

Effective assessment methods for students in higher education institutions

Despite the continued growth of AI and its usage in schools, learning and assessment objectives set by the universities must still be attained. Technological advancements are meant to enhance teaching efforts and not replace the teaching efforts. According to Heny and Pencook (2023), for universities to continue to excel at its core mission of teaching, it must respond to the challenges posed by AI and must work towards training faculty to manage these challenges as opposed to shunning it. "The bulk of these efforts inevitably fall on the shoulders of faculty members who must rapidly understand this unique technology, grapple with its implications for their course goals, teaching strategies, and evaluation techniques and develop methods for seizing gains and mitigating losses in the midst of continuing AI" (Heny & Pencook, 2023, Pg. 1). According to Lydia Lu as cited by Cardona et al (2023), there is a strong need for all stakeholders involved in the education sector to critically understand the effects of AI and education. AI tools may enhance teaching methods and learning outcomes but at a cheaper cost (Cardona et al, 2023). Assessment methods may be developed in a way that makes them responsive to the knowledge and experiences that the students possess (Cardona et al, 2023). Therefore when creating assessments, consideration should be given to aligning the assessment methods with the existing knowledge and experience of the learners. This suggests a learner centered approach that takes into account diverse backgrounds and prior learning of the learners (Cardona et al, 2023). Embracing AI tools such as ChatGPT means thoroughly understanding that there is a cheaper way to enhance teaching, improve learning while at the same time, saving time. One of the objectives of the creation of AI tools was ease of use (Bridgeman et al, 2023). It could help students learn by creating new opportunities for them to learn. As established earlier, current

assessment methods have several potential problems and the usage of AI tools such as ChatGPT may potentially offer new learning opportunities to address these problems. One useful way faculty can employ AI tools to effectively assess students is by modifying the current mode of assessment while maintaining the objectives of assessment. Swiecki et al (2022) suggests practical assignments using an AI environment such as games and simulations can support authentic assessment of students' skills but cautiously advises that educators should be careful to not let AI restrict the pedagogical role of assessment. As suggested by Heny and Pencook (2022), AI tools should only be used as instructional design aides. As AI tools continue to gain popularity, the role of teachers is still a fundamental and critical element in a student's learning process and as such should not be undermined (Owan et al., 2023). Lee (2023) states that there is a need to accept the presence of ChatGPT and lecturers should critically understand how the tool works and take advantage of its weaknesses. As such, lecturers should consider using authentic and personalized assessment methods such as using real life examples and contextually specific assignment or discussion question assessments (Lee, 2023). Lee (2023) further suggests adding personal experiences to questions which can allow students to draw specific conclusions, placing emphasis on assessing the learning process rather than the outcome. Assessments designed to critique papers, creating concept maps enables students to gain a deep understanding of the topic beyond what ChatGPT is able to provide for them in its responses (Lee, 2023). Mohamed et al. (2022) warned that AI was here to stay and there was an urgent need for universities and lecturers to accept its existence and find ways of training and guiding students to use AI ethically.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework on which this research was based is Chickering and Reisser's seven vectors of development (Corey, 2011; Leticia & Bonita, 2000; Norhasni &

Affero, 2012). The seven vectors of Chickering's theory are 1) developing competence, 2) managing emotions, 3) moving through autonomy toward interdependence, 4) developing mature interpersonal relationships, 5) establishing identity, 6) developing purpose and 7) developing integrity. The Chickering theory was a revision of a growing number of student development theories of his time (Chickering, 1969).

For this research, the focus was on vectors number 1 and 7. How would instructors assess students in this era of AI chatbots to develop a set of useful competences while upholding integrity as a learner? The first vector of Chickering's theory of developing competence included intellectual, physical or manual and interpersonal qualities that would be gained through assessments given by educators to learners. In the wake of the AI chatbots, was it possible anymore to have learners develop these qualities if the learners could easily seek the help of AI chatbots to respond to assessments given by their teachers? Intellectual development meant growth in the ability to think and reason. Is this possible anymore? Is the ability of learners to communicate and interact with others (interpersonal skills) still possible? One of the objectives in teaching is to develop learners who are honest and principled. This is where the seventh vector of Chickering's theory comes in. In this era of AI chatbots, would teachers still be able to train students with integrity, students who would not cheat their way to graduation? The genesis of AI chatbots set the two vectors on the balance, with doubt whether higher education institutions would still be able to develop competence and integrity in students. This research, therefore, sought to explore methods that would be used to assess higher education students amidst the existence of AI chatbots.

Research Methodology

This study aimed at exploring and understanding the perception of educators and students, of the contribution and effect of AI chatbots to the assessment methods used by instructors to assess students in universities and colleges. The study examined whether the current methods of assessing students were still effective amidst the usage of AI chatbots by students to help give responses to questions in assessments. With an in-depth probe into the experiences of both instructors and students the study took a phenomenological qualitative approach to research in order to dig into hidden thoughts of respondents to make deductive conclusions.

The study used the phenomenological research design because the researchers sought to understand lived experiences of the respondents (instructors and students) and how the respondents subjectively interpreted their lived experiences (Juma, 2023). Through the phenomenological approach, the research aimed at exploring the lived experiences and perceptions of instructors of how the use of AI chatbots by students influenced effective assessment of students using the existing assessment methods in the universities and colleges which were sampled. The researchers also aimed at learning the perceptions of students on the effectiveness of the assessments they received amidst their usage of AI chatbots when attempting to respond to questions or tasks given in the assessments.

Participants

This research utilized a purposeful sample to recruit instructors and students from two higher education institutions in Ndola, Zambia. The researchers needed to have participants who had an idea of or interacted with AI chatbots like ChatGPT, Bing, Bard and so on. AI chatbots were only introduced in November 2022, so not so many instructors and students may have known or interacted with them. One of the two higher education institutions chosen

had IT and Computer Science students while both utilized e-resources in managing student assessments.

Permission to recruit respondents and collect data from the two institutions was sought through their employees designated to give such permissions. This was either the Human Resource Manager or Academic Head of the institution. Letters were written to them by the Research Board of the University where the researchers worked.

Research Instruments

Semi-structured interview guides were developed by the researchers in order to provide guidance on areas of interest that marched the objectives and theoretical framework of the research. One interview guide for the instructors (Appendix A) and one interview guide for students (Appendix B) were developed. The interviewers were able to probe for deeper responses even with the presence of the interview guide. This probe was meant to dig in the nuances of the experiences and perceptions of the respondents.

Data Analysis and Findings

Lecturer Responses

Knowledge of existence of AI Chatbots

The key aspects of the findings were that most respondents had little to limited information about AI tools and the specificity of them. The information known of them had been acquired through adverts as mentioned by one the respondents. Two respondents mentioned to know more about them and have used them several times.

Benefits of using AI Chatbots

There were several key findings that emerged from the perspectives of university lecturers regarding the benefits that emerged with the use of AI chatbots. The respondents overwhelmingly highlighted the positive impacts of these tools on their teaching practices. They noted that AI chatbots significantly improved their preparation and delivery of lectures by providing quick access to relevant information and assisting in the creation of interactive content. Moreover, the ability of chatbots to summarize resources was deemed invaluable, saving lecturers considerable time by condensing lengthy materials into concise summaries. Furthermore, lecturers appreciated the time-saving aspect of AI chatbots, as these tools automated repetitive tasks and provided instant access to information. This efficiency allowed lecturers to allocate more time and energy towards complex tasks ultimately enhancing the quality of their teaching. However, despite the evident benefits, lecturers also voiced concerns about the widespread encouragement of AI chatbot usage. They cautioned against excessive reliance on technology, fearing it could lead to a decline in critical thinking skills and independence among students.

Knowledge of objectives for student assessment

The research explored the main objectives of assessing university students and several key findings emerged, shedding light on the multifaceted nature of student assessment in higher education. One respondent identified the need to gauge students' understanding of materials covered in their courses as a critical objective for university student assessment. Feedback also emerged as a critical component of the assessment process, serving as a catalyst for enhancing learning strategies. By soliciting feedback from assessments, educators gained valuable insights into students' learning experiences and challenges. This feedback informed the formulation of personalized strategies to address areas of weakness and optimize learning outcomes. Furthermore, assessments played a pivotal role in determining

whether learning had indeed taken place. By evaluating students' performance against predefined learning objectives, educators were able to assess the extent to which students had absorbed and retained knowledge. This aspect of assessment was crucial in providing feedback on the effectiveness of instructional methods and guiding instructional decisions. The findings also highlighted the importance of assessing students' exposure to technology in today's digitized educational landscape. Evaluating students' proficiency with technological tools and platforms provided insights into their readiness to navigate digital learning environments. Skill development emerged as another key objective of student assessment. Assessments went beyond testing knowledge acquisition to evaluate students' development of essential skills such as critical thinking, communication, and problem-solving. Assessments were found to have the potential to influence behavioral changes in students. Problem-solving skills were also identified as a key focus of student assessment. Assessments provided opportunities for students to demonstrate their ability to solve complex problems across various contexts. Ultimately, the primary objective of assessing university students was to ensure the attainment of predefined learning outcomes.

How has AI affected student objectives

From the perspective of the lecturer, the research findings indicate a discernible negative impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on student assessment. Respondents highlighted several aspects where AI has adversely affected learning outcomes, notably by diminishing students' engagement with their own perspectives in responses. The findings also suggest a concerning trend of decreased effort among students in conducting research, gathering information, and synthesizing data due to the reliance on AI. Moreover, it is evident from the findings that AI tools tend to discourage proactive learning behaviors among students, as they often submit responses generated by AI tools without significant input or critical thinking. Some respondents expressed concerns that AI tools have compromised the

alignment of learning objectives with traditional assessment methods, necessitating a revision of student assessment objectives. Consequently, the overarching conclusion drawn from the research is that AI tools do not inherently enhance the learning process. However, it is acknowledged that these tools could potentially contribute to the quality of assignment submissions provided students possess adequate knowledge of how to effectively utilize them and interpret the information provided.

Proposed assessment methods amidst AI usage

The findings in some responses suggested that current traditional assessment methods such as generic assignment have now become inefficient and ineffective amidst the usage of AI. As opposed to applying themselves, students submit AI generated information with no input from themselves. To counter this, the respondents suggested case studies, oral presentations, one on one discussions and analytical assessments to be used instead of the traditional mode assessments of assignment questions and discussion questions. However, a percentage of respondents suggested integrating AI usage into the education system rather than shunning it. Furthermore, it was important for AI usage to be encouraged among students except they should be advised and trained on correct usage of AI. Rather than eliminating the mode of assessments, lecturers should be trained on how to effectively set assessments in consideration of AI usage so that they were still able to meet the set learning objectives. Some respondents suggested one way of integrating AI into school curriculum was for verification of information fed into AI tools such as chatbots by higher education institutions and possible collaboration between academicians and AI developers.

Proposed legal framework for AI usage in Higher Learning Institutions

The majority of the respondents affirmed that AI was here to stay and it was imperative for universities to adapt to this changing technology as opposed to shunning it. One respondent mentioned that in developed countries, they were more advanced in

technology and had already taken into consideration ways in which AI can be used effectively. Developing countries like Zambia are only playing catch up and they therefore needed to establish ground on which AI tools could be used effectively without distorting the objectives of current assessment methods. One of the ways mentioned was that the usage of AI needed to be governed by relevant institutions or the government. Another way was to establish hefty penalties for students who were guilty of AI cheating and these penalties could come from higher education institutions governing bodies. One respondent stated that “there was a need for a legal framework to be formulated to handle penalties on AI cheating, however way that framework would look like”. In addition, another respondent stated that there was a need for AI cheating to be categorized as high level cheating. Some respondents mentioned that there was a need for more research to be done on AI so that it could be properly understood and its capabilities and inefficiencies well defined. This way, AI tools could then be well implemented in higher learning institutions with adequate restrictions on its usage. This also included investment in adequate IT infrastructure by all universities to ensure that AI tools and alike could be well implemented and monitored. Some of the findings suggested that there was now need for universities to consider open book exams which have a time limit on how long a student can take to complete an exam. Traditional ways of assessing students, so far, has remained to be the best therefore there was a need to study how AI could be used to assess students effectively without deviating much from traditional methods of assessment. Some respondents mentioned that one way in which this could be done is by increasing the number of tests and reducing the number of assignments than the other way round. This ensured that the objectives of assessing students in how to write, how to research, and how to critically analyze information could still be retained in that one assignment given to students. The rest of the time, student’s assimilation of knowledge learnt should be assessed through tests and exams. In addition, the grading system should be

changed in universities where universities increased the weight on practical assessments and reduced on theoretical assessments. Theoretical courses should have more practical aspects and assessments on them as well.

Student Responses

Quick responses and learning assistance

Respondents noted that AI tools, particularly ChatGPT, provided quick analyses and concise answers to queries. AI tools were praised for their ability to generate summarized responses, which was seen as advantageous, especially for efficiency in information retrieval. One of the challenges highlighted was the brevity of information provided, often necessitating further expansion or clarification. Respondents appreciated that AI tools listed all relevant information at once, saving time compared to searching across multiple websites. AI tools were commended for their ease of use and time-saving capabilities, particularly beneficial for students and those with overdue assignments.

While AI tools were considered helpful for learning and explaining complex tasks in simpler formats, the respondents noted a lack of passion compared to traditional teaching methods. While generally rated highly for accuracy, respondents acknowledged occasional inconsistencies in responses, especially when compared to their prior knowledge or research. Clear articulation of queries was highlighted as essential to receive accurate responses from AI tools, with language barriers posing a challenge. The respondents also expressed concerns about overreliance on AI tools leading to laziness, emphasizing the importance of independent fact-checking.

Accessibility and critical thinking

The respondents expressed concerns about the ease of access to information provided by AI tools, particularly ChatGPT, without proper citation or critical thinking. They noted instances where information was submitted without thorough consideration. There were

mixed perspectives on the impact of AI tools on critical thinking skills. While some participants believed AI could aid in critical thinking by breaking down topics and providing context, others felt it encouraged laziness and reduced critical thinking engagement. Several respondents highlighted negative impacts on learning, intelligence, and critical thinking skills. They noted a decrease in critical thinking skills and expressed concerns about overreliance on AI tools, which could undermine students' confidence in their own abilities.

Balancing dependency and autonomy

Respondents emphasized the importance of not becoming overly reliant on AI tools and stressed the need for students to develop paraphrasing skills. They suggested using AI tools as guides rather than substitutes for independent learning and critical thinking. Concerns were raised regarding the accuracy of information provided by AI tools, with some participants rating their reliability around 80%. However, participants acknowledged the usefulness of AI tools in providing concise summaries and short notes for better understanding

Dependency and autonomy

Participants expressed concerns about becoming overly dependent on AI tools, leading to a lack of personal initiative and critical thinking in learning processes. While AI tools were acknowledged for their role in aiding research when lecturers were unavailable, participants highlighted the importance of not relying on them for personal decision-making or abdicating responsibility for learning. Participants emphasized the need to understand that AI tools are algorithms and should not be solely relied upon for accurate or comprehensive information. However, some participants noted that AI tools had not significantly impacted them.

There were concerns raised about AI tools hindering learning independence and responsibility, particularly when individuals relied too heavily on them for answers without

engaging in critical thinking or personal research. Participants shared mixed experiences with AI tools, noting instances where they had not yielded impressive results in assignments. However, some participants felt that AI tools had helped them take responsibility for their learning, while others believed they hindered it. Participants emphasized the importance of mentors guiding individuals to avoid seeking easy solutions and to take responsibility for their learning journey. They stressed that AI tools should be used as aids rather than replacements for personal learning efforts.

Honesty and citation

Respondents expressed concerns about the lack of honesty associated with using AI tools, citing issues such as the tools not citing sources and the temptation for students to maintain their grades through dishonest means. Strategies for ensuring honesty included using AI tools for verification and then conducting further research on the topic to enhance understanding and integrity. Participants had mixed feelings regarding the honesty of using AI tools, with some feeling guilty about not acknowledging sources or doing their own work, while others justified their usage by counter-checking responses or using plagiarism checkers. While some participants admitted to using ChatGPT extensively for assignments, others emphasized the importance of not depending entirely on AI tools and using them only to assist in certain areas, not for entire assignments. Participants highlighted the compromise of integrity when using AI tools and stressed the importance of self-discipline, learning, and maintaining academic integrity. Respondent's suggestions included implementing restrictions on AI tool usage, providing more time for assignments, and ensuring flexibility in assessment structures to prevent overreliance on AI tools and encourage independent learning.

Improving accuracy and integration

Respondents emphasized the need for AI tools to be more accurate, ideally achieving 100% accuracy. Suggestions included integrating AI tools into learning management systems

and providing developer packages for students similar to Google's developer programs. Respondents suggested universities should normalize the use of AI tools for learning and provide more honest ways for students to utilize them. They also proposed improvements such as adding citations and references to the information generated by AI tools to enhance academic integrity.

Support for learning and teaching

AI tools were seen as beneficial for summarizing information, assisting struggling students, and aiding lecturers in understanding complex topics. Suggestions included using AI tools for presentations, integrating them into course modules, and assisting lecturers in explaining certain subject matter. Respondents suggested universities should continue using assignments to promote deeper learning and implement plagiarism software to detect improper usage of AI tools in assignments. They also recommended more interactive assessment methods such as oral presentations and practical tests. Respondents highlighted the importance of providing opportunities for students to engage with real business environments and professionals to enhance practical learning experiences.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The research findings reveal a nuanced landscape regarding AI chatbots' impact in higher education, as perceived by both students and lecturers. Student responses showcased a mixed sentiment towards AI tools, appreciating their efficiency and assistance in learning tasks while expressing concerns about over-dependency, diminishing critical thinking, and

integrity issues. Despite the convenience AI tools offer, students emphasized the importance of maintaining personal initiative, critical thinking skills, and academic integrity, suggesting a cautious and balanced approach to AI integration in education. This feedback underscores the need for educators to guide students in responsibly leveraging AI tools as aids rather than replacements for independent learning efforts, fostering a culture of self-discipline and academic integrity.

Conversely, lecturers identified numerous benefits of AI chatbots, including improved lecture preparation, delivery, and time-saving aspects, enhancing teaching practices. However, concerns regarding over-reliance on technology, potential impacts on critical thinking among students, and the need for a revised assessment framework were also highlighted. Lecturers advocated for a legal framework to govern AI usage, emphasizing the importance of collaboration between academia and AI developers to ensure responsible integration and adherence to ethical standards. The conclusions drawn from both student and lecturer perspectives underscore the complexity of AI's role in education, highlighting the necessity of informed guidance, continuous research, and thoughtful integration strategies to maximize the benefits while mitigating potential drawbacks in higher learning institutions.

Recommendations

The research findings on AI chatbots in higher education suggest several recommendations for future exploration and implementation. Further studies should be conducted to track the lasting impact of AI chatbots on student learning outcomes, critical thinking skills, and academic integrity over multiple semesters or academic years. This would provide insights into evolving trends and changes in student behavior and performance. Supplementing quantitative data with qualitative analysis, such as interviews or focus groups, can offer a deeper understanding of students' and lecturers' perceptions, experiences, and challenges related to AI chatbots.

Additionally, exploring ethical considerations surrounding AI chatbot usage is crucial. This includes addressing privacy concerns and biases in AI algorithms. Establishing guidelines and protocols for ethical AI integration in higher education can ensure transparency, fairness, and accountability. Comprehensive training and support programs should be provided for students and lecturers on the effective use of AI chatbots in education. This training should cover critical thinking, information evaluation, citation practices, and responsible AI usage to mitigate risks and maximize benefits. Fostering collaborative partnerships between higher education institutions, AI developers, and regulatory bodies can establish industry standards, best practices, and a legal framework for AI usage in higher learning environments. Dialogue and collaboration are essential to address challenges and leverage AI technology effectively. Exploring innovative assessment strategies that integrate AI chatbots while preserving assessment integrity is vital. This includes investigating alternative assessment methods, adaptive learning technologies, and personalized feedback mechanisms to enhance learning outcomes and engagement. Implementing a system for continuous evaluation and feedback gathering on AI chatbot usage in education is necessary. Addressing these recommendations can contribute to a more informed, ethical, and effective integration of AI chatbots in higher education, ultimately improving teaching and learning experiences for students and lecturers.

References

- Cardona, M. A., Rodríguez, R. J., & Ishmael, K. (2023). *Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Teaching and Learning: Insights and Recommendations*. Office of Educational Technology, U.S Department of Education, Washington DC. Retrieved September 21, 2023, from <https://www2.ed.gov/documents/ai-report/ai-report.pdf>
- Chickering, W. A. (1969). *Education and Identity*. Jossey-Bass.
- Corey, F. (2011). Chickering and Reisser's Seven Vectors of Development: Using the Theory to Assess Three Students. Retrieved from https://friendportfolio.weebly.com/uploads/1/4/0/6/14065890/friend_formal_theory_paper.pdf
- Gokhale, A. A. (2016). The importance of assessment and evaluation in teaching and learning. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(27), 36-43. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7176/JEP/7-27-05>
- Henry, N., & Pennock, A. (2023, June). Generative AI has Arrived. What Does this Mean for Teaching and Learning at UVA? *Report of the Generative AI in Teaching and Learning Task Force*. Retrieved September 21, 2023, from https://provost.virginia.edu/sites/provost/files/gen-ai-in-teaching-learning-final_508.pdf
- Johnson, A. (2023, January 18). *ChatGPT In Schools: Here's Where It's Banned—And How It Could Potentially Help Students*. Retrieved September 20, 2023, from Forbes: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/ariannajohnson/2023/01/18/chatgpt-in-schools-heres-where-its-banned-and-how-it-could-potentially-help-students/?sh=37cb39656e2c>
- Korn, J., & Kelly, S. (2023, January 6). *New York City public schools ban access to AI tool that could help students cheat*. Retrieved September 20, 2023, from CNN Business: <https://edition.cnn.com/2023/01/05/tech/chatgpt-nyc-school-ban/index.html>
- Lau, S., & Guo, P. (2023, September 10). From "Ban It Till We Understand It" to "Resistance is Futile": How University Programming Instructors Plan to Adapt as More Students Use AI Code Generation and Explanation Tools such as ChatGPT and GitHub Copilot. *ICER '23: Proceedings of the 2023 ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research, I*, 106-121. Retrieved September 18, 2023, from <https://doi.org/10.1145/3568813.3600138>
- Lee, J. (2023). *Effective assessment practices for a ChatGPT-enabled world*. Times Higher Education. Retrieved from <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/effective-assessment-practices-chatgpt-enabled-world>
- Leticia, L. L., & Bonita, B. (2000). Chickering's Seven Vectors of Student Development Explained. Retrieved from <http://kvccdocs.com/KVCC/2013-Spring/FY125-OLA/content/L-17/Chickering-Vectors-Explained.pdf>
- Liang, P. P., Morency, L.-P., & Salakhutdinov, R. (2021). Towards Understanding and Mitigating Social Biases in Language Models. *International Conference on Machine Learning*. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2106.13219.pdf>

- McCabe, D. L. (2005). Cheating among college and university students: A North American perspective. *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 1(1), 1-11. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21913/IJEI.v1i1.10>
- Microsoft. (2023, May 25). Governing AI: A Blueprint for the Future. Retrieved September 18, 2023, from <https://query.prod.cms.rt.microsoft.com/cms/api/am/binary/RW14Gtw>
- Mollick, E. (2022, December 14). *ChatGPT Is a Tipping Point for AI*. Retrieved September 18, 2023, from Harvard Business Review: <https://hbr.org/2022/12/chatgpt-is-a-tipping-point-for-ai>
- Nolan, B. (2023, January 30). *Here are the schools and colleges that have banned the use of ChatGPT over plagiarism and misinformation fears*. Retrieved September 20, 2023, from Business Insider: Africa: <https://africa.businessinsider.com/news/here-are-the-schools-and-colleges-that-have-banned-the-use-of-chatgpt-over-plagiarism/q9mykkh>
- Norhasni, A. Z., & Affero, I. (2012, January). Exploring Student Development Theory in Enhancing Learning through Supervision. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 1(1), 213-223. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313567028_Exploring_Student_Development_Theory_in_Enhancing_Learning_through_Supervision
- OpenAI. (2022, November 30). *Introducing ChatGPT*. Retrieved September 19, 2023, from OpenAI: <https://openai.com/blog/chatgpt>
- Owan, V. J., Abang, K. B., Idika, D. O., Etta, E. O., & Bassey, B. A. (2023). Exploring the potential of artificial intelligence tools in educational measurement and assessment. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*. Retrieved 2023, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371733134_Exploring_the_potential_of_artificial_intelligence_tools_in_educational_measurement_and_assessment
- Roose, K. (2023, January 12). *Don't Ban ChatGPT in Schools. Teach With It*. Retrieved September 20, 2023, from The New York Times: <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/01/12/technology/chatgpt-schools-teachers.html>
- Spaulding, D. T., Rockinson-Szapkiw, A. J., & Donnelly, C. (2018). Proctoring online exams: Strategies for assuring academic integrity. *Journal of Online Learning Research*, 4(3), 229-255. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/24748668.2018.1473228>
- Thomas, S. L., & Johnson, S. M. (2008). Successful strategies for recruiting, training, and utilizing proctors for high-stakes testing. *International Journal of Testing*, 8(1), 17-29. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15305050701807715>